

EKALAVYA MODEL RESIDENTIAL SCHOOLS IN ODISHA - AN OVERVIEW

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Introduction

Ekalavya Model Residential Schools are established for the upliftment of ST children to provide them proper education with residential facilities. The Scheduled Tribe population in Odisha are scattered over the area of 69,614 sq.kms, out of the total geographical area of 1,55,707 sq.kms of Odisha. There are 62 Scheduled Tribe communities in Odisha which constitutes 9.6% of the country's total population out of which 13 are Vulnerable Tribal Groups (PVTG). Scheduled Tribes constitute about 23 per cent of the total population of Odisha. Majority of them are found in 17 districts of Odisha. There are higher incidences of poverty marked among the STs in the state of Odisha than other states. The nutritional standard and health condition of Scheduled Tribe communities is relatively lower than the general population. Low Literacy among the people of tribals made them isolate from modern civilization. Superstitions, rituals and spiritual beliefs are different reasons for low literacy. Difference in language, lack of proper guidance, communication gap and different kind of fear made the STs backward in the modern society. Government of Odisha is committed to improving the educational status of SC and ST communities by implementing various interventions like free education, free textbooks and reading and writing materials, scholarships, hostels etc.

Odisha is one of the leading states in India in providing residential schooling facility to ST students. 1721 residential schools and about 6898 hostels for ST and SC students in Odisha provide primary to senior secondary education to more than 4.50 lakh ST/SC students.

TABLE 1 Educational Institutions under ST and SC Development Department in Odisha (2018-19)

Category	No. of Schools/ Colleges
Ekalavya Model Residential Schools	19
Higher Secondary Schools	62
High Schools (Co-Education)	249
Girls High Schools	173
Ashram Schools	700
Secondary Teachers Training Schools	3
Residential Sevashrams	5
Educational Complex for PVTGs (15 ECs upgraded to High Schools)	4
Sevashrams	501
B.Ed. College	1
Kalinga Model Residential Schools	4
Total	1721

Source: Odisha Economy Survey 2018-19, Govt. of Odisha, Bhubaneswar

Hostel Facilities for the ST and SC Students

At present, around 6898 hostels are providing accommodation facility for education to more than 4.50 lakh ST and SC students, out of which around 2.75 lakh are girls (Odisha Economic Survey 2018-19).

Background of Ekalavya Model Residential Schools

The Orissa Model Tribal Education Society supported by the Scheduled Tribe and Scheduled Caste Development Department aims to make positive intervention in the field of tribal education. Since its inception in March 2000, it has set up 27 Ekalavya Model Residential Schools in different parts of Odisha with assistance from Government of India.

Establishment of Model Residential Schools was launched during 1997-98 to provide quality education to the ST students. The Model Residential Schools are called Ekalavya

Model Residential Schools (EMRS) and envisaged on the lines of Navodya Vidyalayas but with State Centered Management.

Establishment of Ekalavya Model Residential Schools(EMRS) in Odisha

In Odisha, as per the guidelines of Ministry of Tribal Affairs, Government of India, a society called the “Odisha Model Tribal Education Society” has been established. This society has been given the charge of the establishment of the Ekalavya Model Residential Schools including construction of buildings. Rs. 2.50 crores was made available for civil construction complexes including the School building, Hostel and Staff quarters etc. for each school.

Ekalavya Model Residential Schools were started functioning since 2000-2001. Table 2 shows the year of sanction and the year of function of Ekalavya Model Residential Schools in 17 different districts of Odisha.

TABLE 2 Year of Establishment and Recognition Status of Ekalavya Model Residential School in 17 Districts of Odisha (2020-21)

S. No	Name of EMRS	District	Year of Sanction	Year of Function
1.	EMRS,Pungar	Koraput	1997-98	2000-01
2.	EMRS,Dhanghera	Mayurbhanj	1997-98	2000-01
3.	EMRS,Bhawanipur	Sundargarh	1997-98	2000-01
4.	EMRS,Siriguda	Rayagada	1997-98	2000-01
5.	EMRS, Ranki	Keonjhar	2001-02	2001-02
6.	EMRS, Chandragiri	Gajapati	2001-02	2001-02
7.	EMRS Mahasingi	Kandhamal	2001-02	2001-02
8.	EMRS, Hirli	Nabarangapur	2001-02	2001-02
9.	EMRS, Laing	Sundargarh	2002-03	2002-03
10.	EMRS, Lahunipada	Sundargarh	2002-03	2002-03
11.	EMRS, Rampilo	Jajpur	2007-08	2007-08
12.	EMRS, Malkangiri	Malkanagir	2010-11	2011-12
13.	EMRS, Nuapada	Nuapada	2010-11	2011-12
14.	EMRS, Bikrampur	Rayagada	2015-16	2018-19
15.	EMRS, Bangirposi	Mayurbhanj	2015-16	2018-19
16.	EMRS, Karanjia	Mayurbhanj	2015-16	2018-19

17.	EMRS, Dumerbahal	Bolangir	2011-12	2018-19
18.	EMRS, Kuarmunda	Sundargarh	2015-16	2018-19
19.	EMRS, Kuchinda	Sambalpur	2015-16	2018-19
20.	EMRS, Phiringia	Kandhamal	2015-16	2020-21
21.	EMRS, Saldahara	Balasore	2016-17	2020-21
22.	EMRS, Kalamati	Deogarh	2016-17	2020-21
23.	EMRS, Kirimara	Jharsuguda	2016-17	2020-21
24.	EMRS, Gidhibasa	Keonjhar	2016-17	2020-21
25.	EMRS, Konga	Koraput	2016-17	2020-21
26.	EMRS, Dhanarabhata	Kalahandi	2011-12	2020-21
27.	EMRS, Bahalda	Mayurbhanj	2011-12	2020-21

Source: Odisha Model Tribal Education Society, Bhubaneswar, Government of Odisha, 2021.

Structure of Ekalavya Model Residential Schools (EMRS)

- Admission to EMRS is done through Selection Committee.
- Land is given by the Government of Odisha for the school, play ground, hostels, residential quarters, etc. free of cost.
- The total number of seats for boys and girls is equal.
- Education is free for the students.
- Each class can have maximum of 60 students in two sections of 30 students each and the total sanctioned strength of the school is 480 students.
- There are 3 sections per class for the three streams in Science, Commerce and Humanities, at the higher secondary level (Class XI and XII).

Mission and Vision of Ekalavya Model Residential Schools

- To provide quality education to the ST students especially in remote tribal areas.
- Ekalavya Model Residential Schools to become centres of excellence providing high quality education to tribal students.
- To extend the services of quality education among the ST students especially in remote tribal areas.

Management of Ekalavya Model Residential Schools

For Management of Ekalavya Model Residential School, the Ministry of Tribal Affairs have suggested to adopt the Andhra Pradesh Residential Schools Society Model.

Procedure for Selection of Teachers in Ekalavya Model Residential Schools

The teaching staff including Principal of each EMRS is selected through an interview made by the (OMTES) at a selected central place. A Selection Committee consisting of Director, ST and SC Development Department, Director, SCSTRTI, Deputy Secretary, OMTES and two subject specialists select the candidates for the teaching posts in EMRS. The appointment of above category of staff is on contractual basis with a monthly consolidated remuneration.

Provision of Incentives for Students in Ekalavya Model Residential Schools

According to the provision made by OMTES, each boy boarder gets Rs. 85/- and each girl boarder gets 115/- as pocket money which is being kept in any nationalized bank by the school authority suitable to them. There is provision to supply two pairs of dress, tie, a pair of shocks and shoes per annum to all the boarders.

Provision of Incentives for Teachers in Ekalavya Model Residential Schools

The performances of individual teachers are reviewed annually and action is taken by the OMTES accordingly.

The objectives of setting of ERMS are to provide quality education upto Secondary and Higher Secondary stage to Scheduled Tribe students in remote areas. The enrollment of these schools in Odisha are in better stage. But the problems of heads of the institutions, problems faced by the teachers and students in Odisha are needed to be taken care of.

Suggestions

The following suggestions may be given for successful management of Ekalavya Model Residential Schools in Odisha:

- Ekalavya Model Residential Schools need to have separate budget plan for infrastructure, recurring and non-recurring expenditure every year.
- The guidelines of EMRS need to indicate the organizational structure, manpower and educational expertise for the Tribal Welfare Residential Educational Institutions Societies at par with Jawahar Navodaya Vidyalaya Samiti Pattern to ensure quality education for ST students.
- Hostels of EMRS needed to be equipped with adequate furniture, equipment, well ventilated rooms, warden rooms, telephone connection, safe drinking water facility, proper toilet facility, kitchen, dinning hall, and sickroom for students.
- EMRS societies need to prescribe standards in selection of teachers and other staff by providing attractive salaries with regular appointment.

- Regular teachers need to be appointed in each EMRS. Steps may be taken by the Government of Odisha in this regard.
- A three /four wheeler vehicle is needed for the students and staff in each EMRS.
- Additional staff quarters need to be constructed for lady teachers.
- Quality food along with necessary amenities may be provided to the students in hostels.
- In-service training programme for teachers need to be organised on regular basis. OMTES need to take steps in this regard.
- There is need of smart classrooms/computer laboratory with internet connectivity/adequate teaching learning materials, laboratory equipments, library books in all EMRS.
- Coaching facilities may be provided to the weaker students.
- Steps may be taken for opening of Junior Red Cross Unit, Scout and Guide, NCC/ NSS Unit and Eco Club in schools.
- There is need of allocation of funds for the organisation of different co-curricular activities like study tour/exposure trip, inter-school science exhibition /science fair for students.

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